

Brunia microphylla Common Cedar Blacktips

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.9 – 1 m in height

Distribution:

This species occurs in the Western Cape, from the Kogelberg and Hottentots Holland Mountains to the Worcester and Slanghoek Mountains, extending eastwards to the Caledon Zwartberg and Babylonstoren near Hermanus, at altitudes from near sea level to approximately 1 300 m.

Importance:

Brunia microphylla is the most widespread species in the subgenus *Raspalia*, occurring in lower-altitude areas of the Western Cape fynbos, often in large populations. Its broad distribution makes it a useful representative for exploring relationships within the Bruniaceae.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 45.6 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 12.53 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.45 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.3% [Single: 7.2%, Duplicated: 91.1%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 48 492.12 kilobases

Contig number: 1 327

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